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OPENING PLENARY

Sustainable SWM in Developing Countries Focusing on Two Faster Growing Economies, India and China, *Sadhan Kumar Ghosh* **India** *Page 1*

SESSION 1A *Generation and Composition 1*

Predicting the Accuracy of Curbside Waste Composition Studies, *Bruce Wilson*, **Canada** *Page 13*

Waste generation rate from household and relevant factors in Okayama city, *Yasuhiro Matsui* **Japan** *Page 25*

Determination of Factors Influencing Waste Composition at Institutions of Higher Education, *Lauren Crawford, Derek Garbarino, Terry Simpson, Eric Smith, Sean Turley, Ronald L. Mersky*, **USA** *Page 29*

SESSION 1B *Landfill 1*

Unsaturated Behaviour of Waste Wood Ash Treated Lateritic Soil, *Kolawole Osinubi, Johnson Oluremi, Adrian Eberemu*, **Nigeria** *Page 36*

Model of a Secure Landfill Using Abandoned Mine Pit; Technical and Economic Imperatives in Poor Developing Nations, *Michael A. Nwachukwu, Ijeoma M. Nwachukwu*, **Nigeria** *Page 50*

Landfill Final Cover and Management of Leachate Seeps below Final Cover, *Ali Khatami*, **USA** *Page 62*

Desiccation Induced Volumetric Shrinkage of Compacted Metakaolin Treated Black Cotton Soil for Use as Hydraulic Barrier System, *George Moses, Kolawole Osinubi*, **Nigeria** *Page 71*

SESSION 1C *Organic Wastes 1*

A Novel Approach to Food Waste To Energy Modeling in the US, *Matthew Franchetti*, **USA** *Page 83*

Brazilian Research in MSW Biogas: How Large Is It and How Far Has It Gone?, *Ruy Quadros, Glícia Vieira dos Santos, André Neiva Tavares, Dr. Sergio Valdir Bajay*, **Brazil** *Page 95*

Sustainable Bio-Waste Management in Finland through Cascade Use of Biomass, Sari Piippo, Eva Pongrácz, **Finland** *Page 106*

SESSION 1D
Policy

Industrial and Energy Policies for Biogas-Based Electricity from Municipal Solid Waste in Brazil, Ruy Quadros, André Neiva Tavares, Glícia Vieira dos Santos, Dr. Sergio Valdir Bajay, **Brazil** *Page 113*

Reduction of Green House Gas Emission Associated with Effective Waste Mangement: Case of South Korea, Yong-Chil Seo, Jang-Soo Lee, Won-Seok Yang, Tai Gyu Lee, **Republic of Korea** *Page 125*

SESSION 2A
Recycling 1

Fractal Spatial Analysis: The Montreal Case Study, Pierre-Alexandre Guillemette, Mathias Glaus, Robert Hausler, **Canada** *Page 131*

SESSION 2B
Environmental Impacts

Effects Of Solid Waste Disposal On Human Being In The Landfill Sites Surrounding Agra City, Sohail Ayub, **India** *Page 142*

Lack of Community Participation in Management of Garbage: Its Impacts on River Water, and Introduction of Rain Water Harvesting as an Alternative to Pipe Borne Water in Lautoka, Fiji Islands, Ajantha Perera, **Fiji Islands** *Page 153*

SESSION 2C
Energy Recovery 1

The Potential for Waste-to-Energy at the US Naval Academy: A Case Study, Patrick Caton, Joshua Schmidt, Christopher Adsit, Christopher Chase, Eric Bermudez, Timothy Kerner, **USA** *Page 161*

Simultaneous Removal of PCDD/Fs and NOx from the Flue Gas of a Municipal Solid Waste Incinerator with a Pilot Plant, Xiaolong Liu, Jian Wang, Xue Wang, Tingyu Zhu, **China** *Page 173*

Brazilian Research in Municipal Solid Waste Biogas: How Large Is It and How Far Has It Gone?

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Abstract^{1,2}: Biogas produced from the degradation of organic waste and its use as an energy source are not new in Brazil. Nonetheless, while industry is gaining interest once more in the subject after a series of failed projects in the past decades, academic research has continued. Based on the mapping of research competencies in the Brazilian universities and research groups, this paper allows understanding the size, content and relevance of research on municipal solid waste (MSW) in Brazil. A good picture of the locally produced scientific knowledge on MSW is critical to expand the use of biogas for energy needs in the country. Strong academy-industry partnerships are of central importance in adapting foreign technologies and developing local ones, as well as training the next generation of experts in the field. This is important given that

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unique solutions are necessary when faced with the particularities of the MSW found throughout the country, as well as differences in climate and precipitation patterns, in comparison with other regions of the world.

Keywords: Municipal solid waste; Biogas; R&D mapping; Snowball sampling.

1. Introduction

This paper presents a brief overview about current research and development (R&D) activities related to the production of biogas from municipal solid waste (MSW) in Brazil for electricity generation. The aim of this effort is to identify opportunities and challenges in this area.

MSW management has been one of the main sanitation problems for the Brazilian municipalities and states. Data from Abrelpe (2013) show that 60% of the Brazilian municipalities dispose of their residues in an inappropriate way, i.e. either in open or in “controlled” landfills. This type of destination corresponds to 42% of the MSW generated in the country.

The Brazilian Southeastern region is responsible for 52.38% of the MSW collected in the country (99.119 tons/day, out of a total of 189.219 tons/day), with 51% being disposed of in an inadequate manner (Abrelpe, 2013). Many are the elements that contribute to this scenario: population density, economic growth and its impact on family consumption and the difficulties in changing the habits of the population towards separating their trash.

On the 2nd of August 2010 was enacted Law 12,305, which created the National Policy on Solid Wastes (NPSW). This law banned all open and controlled landfills from 2015 onward and defined criteria for the final disposal of MSW in sanitary landfills. The law also requires the municipal authorities to elaborate waste management plans. In order to receive funds from the Federal government, such plans should have goals, deadlines to reach these goals and alternatives to treat the wastes, aiming at a progressive reduction of their volume for final disposal.

A recent study identified an electricity generating potential of 536 MW using biogas from sanitary landfills in Brazil (Abrelpe, 2012). In a context of sustainable technology trajectories, cleaner and more intelligent productive systems and more stringent regulatory rules which will lead to a “greener” economy, how do we identify, select and qualify partners for collaboration in the development of technologies aimed at generating electricity from MSW?

The importance of the contribution of external sources of knowledge for innovation in manufacturing and services companies is widely recognized as a distinctive feature underlying the current forces driving competition (Chesbrough 2012; Tidd, Bessant, & Pavitt, 2008).

Yet, few companies have adopted a systemic approach to managing external sources of innovation, be they related to routines for prospecting and selecting sources and partners or to designing and managing partnership agreements. The literature emphasizes that companies lack such capabilities, but it also lacks the proposition of concepts, tools, and methods to fill the gap (Quadros *et al.*, 2014).

This paper addresses a particular aspect of corporate practices concerning the management of external sources for innovation purposes: the prospecting and identification of opportunities to establish R&D and Innovation partnerships with universities and public research institutes.

2. The methodology adopted in the survey

This paper presents partial results of a broad on-going research project commissioned by Endesa concerning the development of technical and institutional settings for using biogas from municipal solid waste (MSW) to generate electricity. One of the responsibilities of the paper's authors in this project is to map research competencies in Brazilian research institutions on this field.

The survey that is being carried out for this mapping has been applied to research groups in Brazilian universities and research institutes, most of them working on frontier technological issues in the following areas: agricultural engineering, environmental engineering; civil engineering; transport engineering and geotechnics, mechanical engineering, chemical engineering, rural engineering, sanitary engineering and environmental engineering. The partial data discussed in this paper was collected between August and December 2014 by means of structured questionnaires sent by email to 57 research groups, out of which 31 replied so far.

The research groups were mapped thanks to information obtained through CNPq's Lattes platform³, as well as from indications of the researcher fellows themselves, following a snowball sampling method (Atkinson and Flint, 2001).

The questions asked to the research fellows were qualitative in nature and sought to highlight, from the interviewees' point of view, their contribution to the fields in which they work. Furthermore, they were also asked about how they evaluate the results of their research to the MSW biogas sector, including electricity generation, when applicable.

The next section of the paper explores some features of the database collected so far, such as the listing of the respondent institutions, their research productivity, their

³ CNPq's Lattes Platform is a digital information system designed and managed by the National Council for Science and Technology Development (CNPq). It is used as an information tool for implementing CNPq's funding programmes. The Lattes Platform includes a directory of research groups and individual CVs, which can be accessed through CNPq's web site (<http://www.cnpq.br>).

regional distribution, the areas of knowledge involved, patents obtained, funding sources and contracts with companies and government institutions.

3. Identification and characterization of the Brazilian research groups working with MSW biogas

The research groups working with issues related to MSW biogas in Brazil are distributed in 12 universities or public research institutes, which are located in 7 Brazilian states from the northeastern (9), southern (1) and southeastern regions (21). They are listed in Table 1.

Of the research groups mapped out, 61% are consolidated, with more than 10 years of experience and including in their teams 22 research fellows considered of excellence due to their research productivity (Table 2). Sanitary and environmental engineering (8 research fellows of levels 1A, 1D and 2), and civil engineering (5 research fellows with levels 1A, 1B and 1D) are the two knowledge areas that stand out in Table 2. In Brazil, CNPq ranks the senior research fellows in levels 1A, 1B, 1C and 2.

The 11 oldest groups were created from 1993 to 1999 in the states of Rio de Janeiro, Pernambuco, Santa Catarina, São Paulo, Bahia and Ceará (35% of the research groups in the current database). They have between 16 and 22 years of existence and, therefore, already have consolidated their research lines. The youngest groups (8 groups, or 26% of the total), with 12 to 15 years of existence, were created at the beginning of the years 2000 in the states of Minas Gerais, São Paulo, Bahia and Pernambuco. One group (UFV in the state of Minas Gerais) has only 3 years of existence. Nonetheless, this group has already reached level 1A, showing their high level of excellence in the area of Sanitary and Environmental Engineering.

The diversity of knowledge areas of the research groups in Brazil, mapped out so far, working with themes related to MSW biogas is impressive. Table 3 shows that the 31 groups cover 21 knowledge areas.

The largest share of groups list several types of engineering as their research area, with a dominance of civil engineering and sanitary and environmental engineering. This is explained by the fact that MSW management in Brazil has been considered, in general, a major problem within sanitary engineering. Only more recently has MSW management been seen as a challenge to be faced in the search to improve environmental conditions in the cities. So far, the use of MSW, or some of their components to produce energy, has not received much attention. Sanitary engineering is a traditional branch of civil engineering and, in the last 20 years, several courses were created in the country in the area of sanitary and environmental engineering.

Table 1: Research groups on MSW biogas in Brazil, their research institutions, the states where they are located and the year the groups were created

State	Institution	Research group or laboratory	Year
Bahia (BA)	Catholic University of Salvador (UCSAL)	Laboratory of Soils	2002
	Federal University of Bahia (UFBA)	Laboratory of Environmental Geotechnics	1999
		Network of Clean Technologies (TECLIM)	1997
Ceará (CE)	Federal University of Ceará (UFC)	Research Group on Separation by Adsorption (GPSA)	1999
		<i>The name of the research group is not available (na)</i>	<i>na</i>
Pernambuco (PE)	Federal University of Pernambuco (UFPE)	Group of Environmental Geotechnics (GEAMB/UFPE)	1994
		Group of Environmental Processes and Technologies (GPTA)	<i>na</i>
		UFPE's Group of Solid Residues (GRS/UFPE)	1994
		Laboratory of Computational Methods for Geomechanics (LMCG)	2003
Minas Gerais (MG)	Federal University of Minas Gerais (UFMG)	Laboratory of Microbiology (DESA)	2000
		<i>The name of the research group is not available</i>	<i>na</i>
		Integrated Solutions for the Management of Solid Wastes (SIGERS) – transport engineering	2001
	Integrated Solutions for the Management of Solid Wastes (SIGERS) – sanitary and environmental engineering	2001	
	Federal University of Viçosa (UFV)	Research Group on Environmental Quality (GPQA)	2012
		<i>The name of the research group is not available</i>	<i>na</i>
<i>The name of the research group is not available</i>		<i>na</i>	
Rio de Janeiro (RJ)	National Institute of Technology	<i>The name of the research group is not available</i>	<i>na</i>
	State University of Rio de Janeiro (UERJ)	Laboratory of Sanitation Engineering (LES)	1993
	Federal University of Rio de Janeiro (UFRJ)	Study Group on Wastes Treatment	1998
		International Virtual Institute on Global Changes (IVIG/COPPE)	1999
		Laboratory of Thermal Machinery (LMT)	<i>na</i>
		Interdisciplinary Laboratory on Environment (LIMA)	1997
São Paulo (SP)	University of São Paulo (USP)	<i>The name of the research group is not available</i>	<i>na</i>
		National Reference Centre on Biomass (CENBIO)	1996
		Laboratory of Soil Mechanics , Department of Geotechnics, School of Engineering of São Carlos	<i>na</i>
		<i>The name of the research group is not available</i>	<i>na</i>
		Research Centre on Solid Wastes (NEPER)	2003
		EESC/USP' Laboratory on Geosynthetics	2001
	State University Júlio de Mesquita Filho (UNESP)	Group of Optimization of Energy Systems (GOSE)	2002
		<i>The name of the research group is not available</i>	<i>na</i>
Santa Catarina (SC)	Federal University of Santa Catarina(UFSC)	Research Laboratory on Solid Wastes (LARESO)	1995

Source: Developed by the authors.

Table 2: Research groups on MSW biogas in Brazil - research productivity, research institutions and knowledge areas

Research productivity rank	Institutions	Knowledge areas
1A	University of São Paulo (USP)	Hydraulics and sanitation
	State University Júlio de Mesquita Filho (UNESP)	Energy
	Federal University of Minas Gerais (UFMG)	Environmental and sanitary engineering
	Federal University of Viçosa (UFV)	Civil engineering
		Environmental and sanitary engineering
Federal University of Rio de Janeiro (UFRJ)	Energy and the environment	
1B	University of São Paulo (USP)	Geotechnics; civil engineering
	Federal University of Pernambuco (UFPE)	Geosciences
	Federal University of Rio de Janeiro (UFRJ)	Civil engineering
1D	University of São Paulo (USP)	Civil engineering
	Federal University of Bahia (UFBA)	Science and technology of materials
		Environmental engineering
	Federal University of Pernambuco (UFPE)	Civil engineering
	Federal University of Ceará (UFC)	Chemical engineering
Hydraulics		
2	Catholic University of Salvador (UCSAL)	Engineering
	University of São Paulo (USP)	Sanitary engineering
	State University of Rio de Janeiro (UERJ)	Environmental and sanitary engineering
	Federal University of Minas Gerais (UFMG)	Environmental and sanitary engineering
		Environmental and sanitary engineering
	Federal University of Pernambuco (UFPE)	Chemical engineering
	Federal University of Santa Catarina (UFSC)	Environmental and sanitary engineering

Source: Developed by the authors.

The research groups are concentrated in a few states, particularly in the Southeastern region (21 groups). Indeed, this situation reflects the concentration of economic development in Brazil, as industrial activity, post-graduate education and research are concentrated in this region. Moreover, the concentration is particularly strong in the state of São Paulo (8 groups). This can be understood bearing in mind that São Paulo accounts for approximately 40% of the Brazilian manufacturing industry and the research fellows working in the state are responsible for around half of the scientific publications produced in the country (Fapesp, 2005).

Table 3: Frequency of research groups working with MSW biogas in Brazil, by knowledge areas

Knowledge areas	Frequency
Environmental analysis and land management	1
Biocatalysis	1
Science and technology of materials	1
Energy	2
Energy and the environment	1
Engineering	1
Agricultural engineering	1
Environmental engineering	1
Civil engineering	5
Transport engineering and geotechnics	1
Mechanical engineering	1
Chemical engineering	2
Rural engineering	1
Sanitary engineering	1
Sanitary and environmental engineering	6
Geosciences	1
Geotechnics	1
Geotechnics in civil engineering	1
Hydraulics	1
Hydraulics and sanitation	1
Total	31

Source: Developed by the authors.

Table 4 illustrates the regional and institutional concentration of the research groups dealing with subjects related to MSW biogas.

Institutional concentration is even more pronounced. Out of the 31 groups mapped out, 20 (64,5%) belong to only 5 leading research institutions, which accounted for 2 or more groups each: the University of São Paulo, the State University Julio de Mesquita Filho, the Federal University of Rio de Janeiro, the Federal University of Minas Gerais and the Federal University of Viçosa. The average number of 4.2 groups per institution in this elite group of universities is remarkably contrasted with the average of 1.57 groups per institution in the remaining universities. These figures reflect the concentration of research activities in Brazil in just a few institutions, which has been pointed out by science and technology (S&T) indicators evaluated by Fapesp (2005).

Patenting activity of Brazilian research groups is quite timid, although this has changed somewhat in recent years, particularly in the elite group of institutions. The total number of patent submissions identified in the survey described in this paper is 20 (see Table 5), which leads to an average of 2.22 patents per group. Only nine research groups (the oldest ones, i.e. those with between 13 and 21 years of existence) obtained

patents before the Brazilian Innovation Act. Similar to the Bay-Dole Act (Pub. L. 96-517, December 12, 1980), the Brazilian Innovation Act (Law No. 10.973, December 2, 2004) recognized ownership rights of intellectual property by S&T institutions (as well as funding institutions) following research developed with public funding. There are no registrations in the Lattes platform after the period in which this law was enforced about patents deposited and/or obtained by research fellows from the groups evaluated here⁴.

Table 4: Frequency of research groups working with MSW biogas, by Brazilian regions, states and research institutions

State	Institution	Freq.	Subtotal	Region
PE	Federal University of Pernambuco (UFPE)	4	4	9
CE	Federal University of Ceará (UFC)	2	2	
BA	University of Salvador (UCSAL)	1	3	
	Federal University of Bahia (UFBA)	2		
SP	University of São Paulo (USP)	6	8	21
	State University Júlio de Mesquita Filho (UNESP)	2		
RJ	National Institute of Technology	1	6	
	State University of Rio de Janeiro (UERJ)	1		
	Federal University of Rio de Janeiro (UFRJ)	4		
MG	Federal University of Minas Gerais (UFMG)	4	7	
	Federal University of Viçosa (UFV)	3		
SC	Federal University of Santa Catarina (UFSC)	1	1	1
Total		31	31	31

Source: Developed by the authors.

Table 5: Frequency of patents submitted by the research groups working with MSW biogas in Brazil

State	Institution	Research group	Number of patents
PE	UFPE	Group of Environmental Geotechnics (GEAMB)	1
		UFPE's Group of Solid Residues (GRS)	1
BA	UFBA	Network of Clean Technologies (TECLIM)	4
RJ	UFRJ	Study Group on Wastes Treatment	1
CE	UFC	Research Group on Separation by Adsorption (GPSA)	1
RJ	UFRJ	International Virtual Institute on Global Changes (IVIG/COPPE)	5
MG	UFMG	Laboratory of Microbiology (DESA)	4
SP	UNESP	Group of Optimization of Energy Systems (GOSE)	2
RJ	INT	The name of the research group is not available	1
Total			20

Source: Developed by the authors.

⁴ In the next step of the research, the National Institute of Industrial Property (INPI)'s site will be assessed in search of information regarding patents deposited by Brazilian universities/research fellows and patents deposited by non-residents in MSW biogas for electricity generation

Given the excellence of some of the research groups mapped out in the survey and the current evaluation system of post-graduation programs in Brazil, which privileges publications in peer-reviewed journals rather than the protection of intellectual property and/or the development of technologies, it is likely that research fellows have given priority to writing articles for publication, despite the incentives found in the Innovation Act.

Table 6 shows that the areas of environmental analysis and land management (5 patents), environmental engineering and sanitary and environmental engineering (4 patents each) hold 65% of the patents found in the survey so far. The research groups which obtained more patents were the International Virtual Institute on Global Changes (IVIG/COPPE/UFRJ), the Clean Technology Network (TECLIM/UFBA) and the Laboratory of Microbiology (DESA/UFMG).

Table 6: Database overview - frequency of patent owner groups and of patents by knowledge areas

State	Institution	Patents	Knowledge areas
Bahia	Federal University of Bahia (UFBA)	4	Environmental engineering
Ceará	Federal University of Ceará (UFC)	1	Chemical Engineering
Pernambuco	Federal University of Pernambuco (UFPE)	1	Geosciences
		1	Civil Engineering
Rio de Janeiro	Federal University of Rio de Janeiro (UFRJ)	1	Civil Engineering
		5	Environmental analysis and land management
	National Institute of Technology	1	Biocatalysis
São Paulo	State University Júlio de Mesquita Filho (UNESP)	2	Energy
Minas Gerais	Federal University of Minas Gerais (UFMG)	4	Sanitary and environmental engineering
Total		20	

Source: Developed by the authors.

The survey revealed that the amount of agreements and contracts between government agencies and research groups / research institutions is much larger than agreements and contracts between companies and research groups.

The current database allowed the identification of 31 sources of private investment (in a total of 36 contracts and agreements) and 66 sources of public funding (in a total of 121 contracts and agreements), covering the 2009/2014 period. Only 5 research groups (from the Federal University of Viçosa, in the state of Minas Gerais, and from the University of São Paulo, in the State of São Paulo) did not use any source of funding (public or private) during this period of time.

In terms of public funding, the Brazilian institutions that granted more often financial resources for the research groups evaluated here were three federal-government-institutions - CNPq (21 times), FINEP (11 times) and CAPES (10 times) – and four states-governments-institutions - FAPESP (5 times), FAPERJ (4 times), FAPESB (3 times) and FAPEMIG (2 times). Furthermore, it is striking the variety of international

funding sources coming from countries such as China, the US, Costa Rica, United Kingdom, Mexico, Argentina, Spain, France, Italy and Canada, as well as the World Bank. A large share of these international sources is from universities.

The Brazilian oil company Petrobras is the main source of private funding, present in 6 projects detected in the survey. The company owns an electric power plant that consumes biogas from the Gramacho Sanitary Landfill. The plant is located in the municipality of Duque de Caxias, state of Rio de Janeiro, distant 6 km from Petrobras' Duque de Caxias oil refinery. Furthermore, some groups also undertake research for Petrobras in the areas of geotechnics (pre-salt layer), biofuels, permeability analysis of mineral protection barriers and geotechnic-geophysics techniques for the study of transportation of contaminants (the last two can potentially be applied to the biogas sector).

Out of the 31 research groups dealt with in the survey, only the Federal University of Rio de Janeiro and the Federal University of Minas Gerais, both located in the Southeastern region of Brazil, developed and implemented biogas projects for electricity generation from municipal solid wastes.

4. Conclusions

This paper evaluates the current state of research on biogas from municipal solid wastes in Brazil. It presents a preliminary analysis of an ongoing project aimed at developing and testing a method for identifying, quantifying, and classifying capabilities, including external R&D partners, of Brazilian research groups in technologies applicable to the MSW biogas industry.

It can be concluded from the analysis carried out here that, in this sector, university-industry relations are formed in a sporadic manner, to solve very specific issues. The MSW biogas sector is relatively recent in the country and, as such, non-consolidated⁵. Nonetheless, some stakeholders are international players. They hold technologies and knowledge already at a mature stage and have their research centers in their country of origin. They were attracted to Brazil by government programs of incentives towards the technological development of a national industry of biogas.

The existence of a biogas industry is an important element to generate demand, develop and internalize state-of-the-art technological research in this area in universities and research institutes. As the national biogas industry is still in its infancy in the country and dependent on external technology (see Quadros et al., 2015), the relationships of the research groups have been much more intense with public funding agencies, both federal government agencies and state governments ones, rather than with companies. These agencies are attempting, through a variety of mechanisms, to stimulate the

⁵ That is not the case of biogas from livestock manure that is used in various plants in rural areas of Brazil to generate heat and electric power. Some of these plants were conceived and built in partnership with Embrapa, a state-owned company responsible for R&D projects for agriculture and livestock.

creation of a market, the nationalization of technologies and the strengthening of interactions between companies and research centers. The Probiogás program of the Ministry of Cities and ANEEL's Call for Projects no. 14/2012 are both steps in this direction.

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